

Supplementary Table 1.

Table 1. Specificity and sensitivity on single antigen or combination antigen in detecting SARS-CoV-2 IgA in convalescent saliva (1-9 month PSO) and pre-pandemic saliva.

		IgA					
		Convalescent (N=72) ^{##}			Pre-pandemic (N=23) [#]		
Antigen	Host	Sensitivity [%]	Pos	Neg	Specificity [%]	Pos	Neg
Spike-f	HEK	17	12	60	96	1	22
S1	CHO	7	5	67	87	3	20
NC-C	<i>E. coli</i>	7	5	67	87	3	20
Spike-f	HEK	7	5	67	96	1	22
S1	CHO						
Spike-f	HEK	4	3	69	96	1	22
NC-C	<i>E.Coli</i>						
S1	CHO	4	3	69	91	2	21
NC-C	<i>E.Coli</i>						
Spike-f	HEK	4	5	67	91	2	21
S1	CHO						
NC-C	<i>E.Coli</i>						

[#] Another 12 independent pre-pandemic saliva samples were used to establish assay cut-offs.

^{*} This sample shows intensity signal at cutoff level.

^{##} Two out of 74 convalescent samples were excluded due to technical reasons.

Fig. S1

1

Fig. S2

2

